

Independence of Time and Space In Quantum Mechanics

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In (1), it is stated that “time flows continuously like a river’ ... and is treated like a classical variable in Quantum Mechanics.” Here, we wish to consider the behaviour of time in quantum situations. We argue that a 4-space sense of time appears in quantum mechanics through $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but only intertwined with E (energy) and p (momentum), i.e. interactions involving these variables. Furthermore, there suggest that there must be a clear measure of t as well as an interaction changing E to use $\exp(-iEt)$ and a clear measure of x and an interaction changing p to use $\exp(ipx)$.

In particular, we note that the classical equation $x/t = v$ ensures that time and x are not on the same footing and this same equation holds in special relativity, so $-Et+px = \text{constant}$ ((1)) which has the appearance of x and t being on the same footing (as well as (x,ct)) is subject to $x/t=v$ (for $x_0=0, t_0=0$). Thus, if $x/t=v$ governs x and t information, then x and t are not independent. It seems that one would require fluctuations from these values. The fluctuations ranges could be linked, but actual t and values within the fluctuations would be independent.

. We suggest it is possible to find a formalism which treats x and t independently from ((1)), but this formalism must be intertwined with E and p. In particular, one has free particle quantum mechanics in which $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$. X and t are decoupled in this scenario and so appear as independent because there is no notion of $x/t=v$ when dealing with quantum type interactions. When dealing with such interactions, one uses the probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but this begs the question: How is this factor really used? We suggest that one must consider the following. Given $\exp(ipx)$, one uses it if p changes and there is a distinct measure of changing x in the problem. This scenario applies to two-slit interference, bound states with $V(x)$ and one dimensional reflection-refraction at a point $x=0$. Given $\exp(-iEt)$, one uses it if there is a distinct interaction involving E, i.e. it changes and there is a distinct measure in time. Thus, two-slit interference, one dimensional reflection-refraction and elastic scattering from a $V(x)$ are out because they don't involve changes in E. A bound state with $V(x)$ certainly involves changes in E, but does not have a direct measure of time t (independent of x). A bound state with $V(x,t)$, however, does have a direct measure of t (being independent of x) and also involves energy changing and so $\exp(-iEt)$ may be used in this case, as will be shown.

Special Relativity, Newtonian Mechanics and Time

Newtonian mechanics seeks to obtain $x(t)$ which shows that x (or y, z for that matter) are not independent of time. There is no sense of 4-space in Newtonian mechanics. 4-space appears in special relativity because the Lorentz transform acts on the 4-vector (x,y,z, ct) which is seemingly independent in the four variables, but really is not. To see this, consider the simpler 2-dimensional case:

$$\begin{aligned} |g(v) \ v/c \ g(v) \ | \ |x| \quad ((2)) \quad g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \\ |v/cg(v) \ g(v) \ | \ |ct| \end{aligned}$$

The vector (x, ct) appears to treat x and ct as independent variables, but the presence of:

$$v = x/t \text{ for } x_0=0, t_0=0 \quad ((3))$$

The matrix of ((2)) shows that this is not the case. For x and t to be independent, one cannot use an equation which treats them differently as ((3)) does. Thus, x and t are not independent in special relativity.

Special Relativity and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

Even though $x/t=v$ holds for special relativity, we suggest that using the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad (= \text{classical relativistic and nonrelativistic action with } x/t=v) \quad ((4))$$

allows one to define uncertain regions:

$$\Delta x = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t = \hbar/E \quad ((5))$$

It is within these uncertainty relations that x and t become independent and these are directly linked to an interaction. Thus, $x=vt$ still holds on average and x and t are not independent in this case, but this has nothing to do with an interaction. The interaction is described by:

$$\exp(ipx) \exp(-iEt) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is not linked to $x=vt$ and two-slit interference and 1-dimensional reflection-refraction at an $n_1 \rightarrow n_2$ index of refraction junction show that there is non-classical physics present. We suggest that this non-classical physics involves independence of t and x , just as ((5)) are independent. As a result, x and t are taken to be independent in ((6)). This begs the question: How should one use ((6))?

How To Use $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

At first, it seems that one would use $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ in a classical manner, applying x and t values subject to $x=vt$. We suggest, however, that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ shows that interactions in t and x are linked with probability regions associated with both variables (i.e. ((5))). Thus, a p , which delivers an impulse hit does not act at a single x point, but there is a probability range of \hbar/p . Thus, a particle may interact with both slits of a 2-slit apparatus if they are about \hbar/p apart. This means that x is not certain. We argue that \hbar/E means that time is not certain either and so does not really flow like a river when interactions occur. The question then becomes: How does one apply $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

We suggest the following scheme:

((7a)) $\exp(ipx)$ is used if p changes in an interaction and there is a measure of x which shows how it may change

((7b)) $\exp(-iEt)$ is used if an interaction changes E and there is a measure which shows how t changes, independent of x .

The scheme of ((7)) involves both x,t and p,E and must involve interactions. A free particle moving in space follows $x=vt$. It is when it interacts that one must use ((7)) because one does not have Newtonian interaction at a point x,t . Newtonian mechanics, however, works very well in the classical world, but this is because \hbar/p and \hbar/E are almost 0, giving the sense of interaction at a point x,t . In situations in which ((5)) are not 0, one must reject interaction at an x,t .

We now consider a series of examples.

Examples of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

In ((7b)), we argued that the use of $\exp(-iEt)$ must involve an interaction which changes E . Thus, 2-slit interference calculations, which do not change the magnitude of p , elastic scattering from $V(x)$ and one dimensional reflection-refraction from an n_1-n_2 index of refraction junction at $x=0$ are not linked with $\exp(-iEt)$. One must use $\exp(ipx)$ for these, because p changes in all and there is a measure of x in all of these problems, i.e. the separation of the slits, the n_1-n_2 junction at $x=0$ and $V(x)$ in the elastic scattering.

We next consider a single particle quantum bound state in $V(x)$. In such a case, there are hits to $\exp(ipx)$ which change p and there is a direct measure of x because of $V(x)$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ may be used. On the other hand, there is a change in energy certainly because as p changes so does E , but there is no measure in time independent of x and so one does not use $\exp(-iEt)$. A bound state calculation yields an E value and this may be applied to an overall $\exp(-iEt)$, but this is only used if ((7b)) applies, we argue.

Finally, we consider $V(x,t)$. This treats x and t as independent. One may fix x in which case there is no measure in x , only in t . $V(x,t)$ represents changes in energy and so ((7b)) applies. Thus, we argue that one should be able to write:

$$W(x=x_1, t) = \text{Sum over } a(p,x) \exp(-i pp/2m t) \quad (\text{nonrelativistic}) \quad ((8))$$

This should lead to:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{Sum over } p, a(p,x) \exp(-ipp/2m t) + V(x_1,t) W(x_1,t) = E W(x_1,t) \quad ((9))$$

Using: $V(x_1,t) = \text{Sum over } b V(b,x_1) \exp(ibt)$ one has:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} a(p,x_1) + \text{Sum over } V(b,x_1) a(pp/2m-b) = E a(p, x_1) \quad ((10))$$

For a component p , i.e. $pp/2m$. (We assume $a(p,x_1)=a(-p,x_1)$.)

Unlike the x case, one cannot localize in time and so there is no $W(x_1, t \rightarrow \infty) = 0$.

Conclusion

In this note, we try to consider the relationship of x and t . Classically $x/t=v$, meaning that even in special relativity these variables cannot be independent despite the form (x,ct) and $-Et+px = \text{constant}$. The reason for the lack of independence is the presence of v in the Lorentz transform matrix which implies $v=x/t$ for $x_0=0$ and $t_0=0$. As long as $x/t=v$ is present, one does not have independence of x and t . We suggest, however, that there is a case in which they become independent and that is free particle quantum mechanics which we argue follows from $A = -Et+px$. Even though one may consider an x and t from $x/t=v$, one has $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. It is x and t values within these ranges which are independent of each other and $x=vt$, even though the lengths of the ranges are linked through $0 = -E \Delta t + p \Delta x$. During an interaction, one may have independent probabilistic changes of x and t for a given p and E which are interacting. We suggest that this is why a particle interferes at a 2-slit apparatus with slits separated about \hbar/p . It interacts with both slits.

\hbar/p and \hbar/E lead to the probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and we try to provide rules for using this function. We suggest that x and t are independent in this form. $\exp(ipx)$ is used (without $\exp(-iEt)$), if p changes and there is a distinct measure of x in the problem independent of t . This applies to 2-slit calculations, elastic scattering from $V(x)$ and 1-D reflection-refraction from an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction at $x=0$. In the case of a single particle bound state in $V(x)$, there is a clear measure of x and p changes. In the case of $\exp(-iEt)$, there is also an interaction which changes E , but no measure for t independent of x .

. In the case of $V(x,t)$ for $x=x_1$, however, there is an interaction which changes E and a clear measure of t independent of x , in other words, one does not introduce a measure in time by replacing x through $x=vt$.

References

1. Connerade, J.-P. The Arrow of Time in Quantum Theory (Oct. 2025)
<https://www.mdpi.com/2218-2004/13/11/86>